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Research Article

**STUDY OF EFFECTIVENESS OF *PORTULACA QUADRIFIDA* IN
THE TREATMENT OF PEDICULOSIS IN KOTNOOR VILLAGE
OF KALABURAGI****Mohammed Arshad*¹, Afroj Jakir Patel², Sameer Aslam Patel³, Mubin Rajmahammad
Shaikh⁴, Arqam Kamil Qazi⁵ and Hassan Naushad Ali Siddiqui⁶**¹⁻⁶ Ayesha college of Pharmacy. Kalaburagi, Karnataka, India.**Abstract:**

Head lice also called *Pediculus humanus Capitis*, head lice are parasitic insects found on the human head and scalp. Having head lice is very common, however, there is no reliable data on how many people get head lice in each year. Head lice can cause an itchy scalp and other symptoms especially for children, and can be difficult to get rid of. so therefore, In the present study, petroleum ether and methanolic extracts of *Portulaca quadrifida* were tested against the *pediculus humanus capitis* by simple filter paper diffusion method.

The methanolic extract showed 97.1% mortality in 30 minutes and 100% mortality in 60 minutes whereas petroleum ether extracts showed 89.5% mortality in 30 minutes and 100% mortality in 60 minutes. In order to reduce the mortality time, the extracts are mixed with carrier oil like castor oil, coconut oil and olive oil. The methanolic extract with all the three-carrier oil showed significant reduction in mortality in 30 minutes whereas petroleum ether showed moderate antilice effect. All the results were well compared with benzoyl benzoate (25% w/v) as standard.

Keywords: *Portulaca quadrifida*, Antilice activity, Filter paper diffusion, *Pediculosis*

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INTRODUCTION:

Lice live among human hairs and feed on blood from the scalp. Head lice problem are common, especially for kids¹. They spread easily from person to person or thought direct head to head (hair to hair) contact (Figure 01). Transmission can also occur through personal belongings of an infested individual like combs, brushes, hats (Figure 02).²

Figure 01: Head to Head Contact

Figure 02: personal belongings (Combs)

Their bites can make a child's scalp itchy and irritated, and scratching can lead to infection³. lice also transmit, pathogens causing human diseases.⁴ and sometimes they are tough to get rid of. Therefore, it is necessary to do research for a potent and safe antilice drug.

As we all know in the present situation medicinal plants are very much influenced by the researchers because of its minimal or no side effects. India is sitting on a gold mine of well-recorded and well-

practiced knowledge of traditional herbal medicine⁵. *Portulaca quadrifida* is one of the Indian medicinal plant belongs to the family of Portulacaceae. It is widely distributed in the tropical parts of India, Bangladesh and Srilanka.^{6,7} Based on the traditional value of *Portulaca quadrifida* still many activities are yet to be proven scientifically.

METHODOLOGY AND RESULT:

Plant material: Fresh plant material of *Portulaca quadrifida* was collected from the local fields of deccan areas of India (Hyderabad and Gulbarga). The plant specimen was identified and authenticated by P. V. Prasanna, Incharge Scientist 'F'. Deccan Regional Centre, Hyderabad-48, Botanical Survey of India. **(With a Voucher No. BSI/DRC/23-24/Tech./1007)**. Then the plant was washed under tap water to remove debris and dried under shade for 10 days. The dried leaves were size reduced to coarse powder in a grinder. **Extraction:** The coarse powder of *Portulaca quadrifida* (500 gm) extracted with Petroleum ether and Methanol by soxhlet extraction technique (figure 03).

Figure 03: Extraction by Soxhlet extraction technique.

All the extracts were concentrated using Rotary vacuum evaporator and kept in a desiccator until further studies the color, consistency and percentage yield were observed⁸. (Table 01)

Table 01: Observation of Percentage yield and colour consistency

S. No.	Extract	Nature of Extract	Colour	Weight (gm)	% Yield (w/w)
1.	Petroleum Ether (40-60°C)	Semi solid	Brownish Yellow	6.54	1.31
2.	Methanol		Green	51.59	10.31

Collection of head lice:

Adult *Pediculus Humanus Capitis* were collected from government school children between the age group of 3 to 12 with the approval of the teachers residing in Kotnoor village, Gulbarga district. The lice were collected by combing the children's scalp. after combing, the lice were carefully collected from the white sheet paper kept in front of subjects (Childrens) and also removed from the teeth of the comb into plastic boxes. All the subjects had not been treated with any anti-lice products for the preceding two months. (Figure 04)

Figure 04: Collection of Lice.

Filter paper diffusion method:

Now a days filter paper assays in Petri dishes are common bioassay method to determine the level of topical insecticides resistance in head lice which provides informative and comparable results. insecticide treated lices are likely able to continue blood feeding and blood injection alter the availability of insecticide or the physiology of louse modify subsequent mortality so it was decided to feed head lice with blood meal by placing the lice on the bare lower leg of one of the authors after collection from the host. Microscopic examination was done in the midgut region and confirmed the blood ingestion. Colony of *Pediculus humanus capitis* was collected by combing the hair of 20-25 infected children at the age group of 3-12. Adult lice were placed in small plastic containers (50 ml polypropylene containers containing 1.5 CM human hair tufts). the mouth was covered with nylon mesh (1 strand/mm) to permit ventilation. for this study the hair tufts were coated with test drugs.

the activity was carried out at $37 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $65 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity in dark room using water as control. In the majority of situations, carrier oil has sufficient suffocating capabilities to make almost any mixture of essential and carrier oil effective in killing lice and possible effectiveness of penetration using lipid-based compounds. So the extract was mixed with the different carrier oils like coconut oil, castor oil and olive oil in the ratio of 10% 20% and 30% and performed the anti-lice activity⁹. (Table 02)

ANTI LICE ACTIVITY

Table: 02: Effects of Petroleum ether extract (PEPQ) and Methanol extract (MEPQ) of *Portulaca quadrifida* against *Pediculus humanus capitis*

Sl.No	Number of Lice	Test Drug	Concentration On (gm/ml)	Average mortality % in 30 min	Average mortality % in 60 Min
01	20	Distilled Water			
02	20	Benzyl Benzoate (Standard)	10%	60	100
			20%	90	100
			30%	95	100
03	20	PEPQ + Coconut oil	10%	55	95
			20%	75	100
			30%	100	100
		MEPQ +	10%	55	95
			20%	70	100

	Coconut oil	30%	100	100
		10%	45	95
	PEPQ + Castor oil	20%	55	100
		30%	95	100
		10%	50	100
	MEPQ + Castor oil	20%	60	100
		30%	100	100
		10%	50	90
	PEPQ + Olive oil	20%	60	100
		30%	100	100
		10%	45	95
	MEPQ + Olive oil	20%	65	100
		30%	95	100

CONCLUSION:

The current study provide scientific basis for the ethnomedical use of this plant as antilice application. It is concluded that it can be optimistic that the present work proved *Portulaca quadrifida* target in the design of a drug for the treatment of lice without causing any adverse influences on eyes and head, to alleviate the suffering the affected individuals. The above study require further investigation for the exact mechanism of action, to develop safe herbal formulation which can result in complementary to those existing pediculocidal agent, which are though acts efficiently they are neurotoxic and induced resistance. So, this provides nontoxic alternative options for head lice treatment.

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REFERENCES:

1. <https://hairdoc.in/all-about-hair/head-lice/>
2. Canadian Paediatric Society(CPS), Head Lice Infestations: A Clinical Update. Infectious Diseases and Immunization Committee, Pediatric Child Health 2004, 9, 647.

3. Jacomo V, Kelly PJ, Raoult D. Natural history of Bartonella infections (an exception to Koch's postulate). Clin Diagn Lab Immunol. 2002;9:8–18. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
4. Raoult D, Roux V. The body louse as a vector of reemerging human diseases. Clin Infect Dis. 1999;29:888–911. 10.1086/520454 [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
5. Rafiq *Et al.* Experimental studies on wound healing properties of andrographis echiodides (L.) Nees in wistar albino rats. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. 2016: 5 (6). 1522 – 1528.
6. Shaik Mohd Khasim and Dr. E. P. Kumar. Antimicrobial activity and in vitro anticarcinogenic properties of ‘portulaca quadrifida linn’ on colon cancer using different extracts. wjpr. 2015; 4 (11): 1644 - 1656.
7. Shahwan and Gacem. Neuroprotective antioxidant effect of portulaca quadrifida linn. leaves extract on immobilization stress-induced changes in rat's brain. Asian J Pharm Clin Research. 2018; 11 (10): 378-381
8. Anbu Jeba Sunil son J, Suraj R, Anandaraja gopal K, Rejitha G, Vignesh M and Promwicht P. Preliminary phytochemical analysis, elemental determination and antibacterial screening of *Codiumdecortatum*-A marine green

- algae. Intentional Journal of Bio Chem. 2009; 3: 84–89.
9. Picollo MI, Vassena CV, Mougabure Cueto GA, Vernetti M, Zerba EN. Resistance to insecticides and effect of synergists on permethrin toxicity in *Pediculus capitis* (Anoplura: Pediculidae) from Buenos Aires. Journal of Med Entomol 2000; 37: 721-725.